

Human Robot Interaction in Rehabilitation: a Case Study

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Abstract—The inherent reliability and safety of collaborative robots allow their application in the healthcare industry, e.g. for neuromuscular rehabilitation. This work proposes a mechatronic implementation of a platform for rehabilitation practices. A case study has been developed with different control laws of the robot for the restoring of the coordination of upper limbs through grasping exercises. Preliminary experiments are conducted on ten healthy volunteers. No adverse events occurred and trajectory and force data were collected in order to track the therapy. Results show that the exercise is sufficiently simple and non-stressing with the provided robotic law.

Index Terms—collaborative robotics, rehabilitation robotics, human-robot interaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaborative robots (cobots) are a new category of robots able to cooperate with humans in a shared environment [1]. Activities involving Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) are promising solutions to achieve higher and more flexible productivity. The combination of the decision-making ability of humans with the intrinsic characteristics of robots (repeatability and accuracy), turns out to be the winning strategy to increase productivity. The use of cobots can be also exploited in fields of applications different from the industrial ones, such as the healthcare sector. However, while collaborative robots in industry cooperate with factory workers, robots in rehabilitation have two different main types of users: the therapists and the patients, which are usually physically attached to the robot's end-effector [2].

Robot-assisted therapy overcome the limitations of the traditional therapy, providing intensive and task-specific solutions for each patient [3]. A further benefit is noted in the contribution to the technological evolution of machines for muscular and cognitive training [4], as well as their use in the assistance of subjects with low residual motor abilities. Moreover, the quantification of the training is enabled, measuring the force, velocity and the Range of Motion (ROM) of a subject during the therapy. To use the robot within therapy sessions, the system has to be adapted with respect to the human limb in terms of ROM, number of degrees of freedom (DOFs) and segments size [5]. The efficiency of robot-based rehabilitation is confirmed by the literature, producing great results in the therapy with more intensive long-lasting exercises [6].

This abstract proposes a mechatronic implementation of a platform for rehabilitation practices. A case study has been developed with different control laws of the robot for the

restoring of the coordination of upper limbs. In the task the subject handles the robot trying to grasp a target randomly placed on a workbench. The movement follows a planned trajectory and the robot can help or hinder the movement.

II. REHABILITATION FRAMEWORK

The system is shown in Fig. 1 (a). The cobot used is the Universal Robots UR5e. The human's hand is connected to the end-effector of the robot by a custom handle to execute standard rehabilitation exercises which involves patient's arm recovery and a partial finger's rehabilitation (see Fig. 1 (b)). The exercise is executed in the frame area, delimited by a white rectangle (53 cm x 34.5 cm) containing a target object whose position is dynamically recorder by a Cognex Smart Camera.

Three force controls are developed to build up the exercise:

- *Freedriver Law*: the robot generates a torque on the 6th robot's joint to assist the rotation of the forearm in order to compensate for friction. The law is realized by a cubic polynomial function.
- *Impedance Control Law*: it is based on the actual pose of the Tool Centre Point (TCP) of the robot with respect to the planned trajectory and regulates the output forces/torques generated to maintain that trajectory.
- *Assistive and Resistive Law*: it sets the magnitude and direction of the robot's force acting along the planned trajectory between TCP and target.

The exercise trains the ability of neurological patients to follow a given trajectory, chosen by the caregiver. In particular,

Fig. 1. (a) Rehabilitation station; (b) handle for the grasping exercise.

Fig. 2. Actual (blue) vs planned (green) trajectory in hard mode.

the exercise aims at restoring the proprioceptive abilities, helping the subject to perform repetitive movements and restoring the muscular activity. The phases of the exercise are are:

- 1) The caregiver places the target and configure the manipulator in front of the subject in a comfortable position.
- 2) The caregiver measures the anthropometric parameters, as the distance between the centre of the hand and the middle phalanx of the middle finger, to be added in the program.
- 3) The robot's end-effector measures some baseline features of the subject (i.e., the force exerted in a relax state and during the maximal effort).
- 4) The caregiver chooses the number of repetitions and the intensity of the exercise (*Easy*, *Medium* and *Hard*).

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Before conducting the experiment on patients, the exercise was tested on ten healthy volunteers (8 male and 2 female with an average of 30 years old). Each subject has been instructed on all the steps of the exercise and supervised throughout its duration. The data acquisition protocol consists of five repetitions in easy, medium, and hard mode with the right and left arm. The data were post-processed in Matlab, where the outliers were deleted and features have been extracted in terms of trajectory and force. The trajectory generated by the subject's hand during the exercise to reach the target is calculated based on the coordinates given by the variation of the robot's TCP pose during the performance. Fig. 2 represents as an example the actual trajectory and the planned one of a subject in one modality. The trajectory's error is defined as the difference between the trajectory and the planned one. The quantitative results from the trajectory analysis are listed in Tab. I.

The largest mean error is in the easy mode, with an overall value of 0.0428 ± 0.020 m. Instead, the medium mode has the smallest overall mean error with a value of 0.032 ± 0.011 m. Since subjects without neurological problems can easily plan trajectories and manage to reach the target, the error between the planned and the measured trajectory is low.

Force data recorded by the robot's TCP are listed on Tab. II, where the mean, median, minimum (min), and maximum

TABLE I
MEAN ERROR BETWEEN THE PLANNED AND THE MEASURED TRAJECTORY.

Mean error \pm std (m)		
<i>Easy Mode</i>	<i>R</i>	0.0424 ± 0.011
	<i>L</i>	0.0432 ± 0.018
<i>Medium Mode</i>	<i>R</i>	0.039 ± 0.013
	<i>L</i>	0.0347 ± 0.009
<i>Hard Mode</i>	<i>R</i>	0.0427 ± 0.011
	<i>L</i>	0.0312 ± 0.016

TABLE II
MEAN ERROR BETWEEN THE PLANNED AND THE MEASURED TRAJECTORY.

		Mean force \pm std (N)	Median force \pm std (N)	Min force \pm std (N)	Max force \pm std (N)
<i>Easy Mode</i>	<i>R</i>	11.72 ± 7.55	11.65 ± 8.30	6.62 ± 2.88	18.51 ± 11.21
	<i>L</i>	11.98 ± 4.78	10.97 ± 5.31	4.28 ± 3.10	22.63 ± 6.22
<i>Medium Mode</i>	<i>R</i>	17.48 ± 9.71	13.29 ± 10.25	13.35 ± 5.38	25.68 ± 12.15
	<i>L</i>	13.37 ± 5.65	9.51 ± 6.02	9.75 ± 4.14	21.99 ± 8.40
<i>Hard Mode</i>	<i>R</i>	16.13 ± 7.87	16.42 ± 8.62	6.30 ± 3.38	26.24 ± 12.30
	<i>L</i>	11.02 ± 4.26	11.13 ± 4.24	5.38 ± 2.71	17.21 ± 6.37

(max) force values are reported with the standard deviation (std) for all subjects in the three modes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The high safety and light weight of the cobots, added to their high precision and repeatability, allow their use for rehabilitation practices, with advantages for both the patient and the operator. The application presented in this paper has been validated by the first experiments on healthy subjects, confirming that the control laws provided the expected results and that the exercise is sufficiently simple and non-stressful.

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